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Effect of Non-Aqueous Solvents on Depolarising Action of Cadmium (II)-N-[(β -Aminoethyl)]-Ethanolamine Complexes at D.M.E.*

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THE electrochemical studies of cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes have been carried out at dropping mercury electrode. Two complexes with metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 have been reported at pH 6.6 ± 0.1 and temperature 303°K . Stepwise formation constants of cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes have been determined in both aqueous and aqueous non-aqueous mixed media. The studies have also been extended to the effect of formamide, dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), methanol, *n*-propanol and isopropanol on the formation constants of the complexes. The effects of ligand concentration on complexation reaction have been examined in terms of relative distribution of metal and ligand in solution.

The importance of amines and several other nitrogen-containing compounds has been recognised in the biochemical, analytical and pharmaceutical fields. Electroanalytical investigation of various metal ions with nitrogen-containing ligands are thus useful and recently studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁵. However, there is no reference to the pursuit of polarographic studies on the cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes, therefore, the present investigation were undertaken.

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Experimental

A manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer acting as a current recorder was used in all the investigations. The dropping mercury electrodes had the characteristics $m=1.8 \text{ mg. sec}^{-1}$ and $t=4.3 \text{ sec. (open circuit)}$. Chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solvents were purified, wherever necessary, by standard methods.

In each system the concentration of Cd(II) was $5 \times 10^{-4} M$. Ionic strength (μ) was $1.0 M$ maintained constant by adding requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate in all the test solutions. The pH was maintained 6.6 ± 0.1 by Toshiniwal pH meter. Purified nitrogen was presaturated with the given aqueous-nonaqueous solvent mixture was passed for thirty minutes to remove dissolved oxygen in each test solution. Temperature was kept constant at 303°K by the help of Haake type ultrathermostat.

Results and Discussion

The reversibility of reduction with involvement of two electrons and with controlled diffusion in aqueous and aquo-nonaqueous mixed media were concluded for cadmium-N-[(β -aminoethyl)] ethanolamine system, from the slopes (31 ± 1) of log plots and proportionality of i_d and $\sqrt{h}$ respectively at 303°K .

To investigate the effect of change of ligand concentration, polarograms of 0.05 mM cadmium(II) mixed with various concentration (0.0 to $0.05 M$) of N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine were recorded. The shift in half-wave potential to more negative values, alongwith a decrease in diffusion current (i_d) on increasing ligand concentration, indicated the formation of complexes in each system. The nature of wave did not change at higher concentrations of ligand.

The values of overall formation constants, evaluated by DeFord-Hume's method⁶ are comprehended below :

Overall formation Constants of Cd(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine Complexes by DeFord-Hume's Method.

Solvent Media	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
Pure aqueous	7.14	9.36
40% Methanol + Aqueous	8.54	9.07
60% Methanol + Aqueous	9.11	9.54
25% DMSO + Aqueous	8.74	10.00
40% DMSO + Aqueous	9.47	11.13
40% Isopropanol + Aqueous	6.84	7.80
60% Isopropanol + Aqueous	6.92	8.14
25% N-Propanol + Aqueous	7.00	7.81
40% N-Propanol + Aqueous	6.89	7.63
25% Formamide + Aqueous	6.25	7.69
40% Formamide + Aqueous	6.90	7.20
60% Formamide + Aqueous	6.84	7.11

It has been observed from the values of overall formation constants that the increase in percentage of methanol and DMSO makes the values of overall formation constant to increase. This may be attributed to the less solvation of the cadmium ion by methanol or DMSO than by water, if solvation is considered to be the only factor affecting the overall formation constant^{8,9}. Otherwise there are many other factors which can affect formation constant viz. density, dielectric constant⁹, viscosity¹⁰, may also be effective in this regard. Moreover ion-pair formation¹¹ plays its role in this case. The increase in the values of overall formation constants in aqueous-nonaqueous media is in complete agreement with similar studies by other workers^{12,13}.

In case of isopropanol-water, *n*-propanol-water and formamide water mixed media of various compositions, the values of overall-formation constants are less than those are in pure water.

The relative distribution of the simple Cd(II) and complexed with N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine as function of ligand concentration advocates that the amount of Cd(II) decreases as ligand concentration increases⁷.

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Synthesis of *p*-Alkyl-(2-benzimidazolyl)-methyl-aminobenzoates and Corresponding Hydrazides as Possible Antimalarial Agents

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A series of esters of *p*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)methyl-aminobenzoic acid (I, Y=OR) has been synthesised. One such ester (Y=OEt) on hydrazinolysis furnished the corresponding hydrazide (I, Y=NH.NH₂) which when condensed with different aromatic aldehydes yielded Schiff's bases (I, Y=NH.N=CHR). Reduction of Schiff's base with sodium-borohydride proceeded smoothly to give I (Y=NH.NHCH₂R). Representative compounds when screened, were found inactive as antimalarial.

A number of benzimidazoles have been synthesised and tested as antimalarial agents^{1,2}. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise such substituted benzimidazole derivatives containing *p*-aminobenzoic acid. The different esters and hydrazides of *p*-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoic acid have been prepared³. The hydrazide was then condensed with aldehydes⁴ and the Schiff's bases thus obtained were reduced to the corresponding secondary amines⁵.

Bio-Assay :

Eleven compounds were screened for antimalarial activity against *P. berghei*-Albino Mice (Swiss) model. None of them was found to be active as antimalarial.

Specification of Host-(Wt = 18-20 gm), sex-male Inoculum : 1 × 10⁶ infected Red cells/animal in 0.25 ml.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are not corrected. Infrared were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer in KBr.

Ethyl-p-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoates ;
(I, Y = OC₂H₅)

Equimolar quantities of 2-chloromethyl-benzimidazole and ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate were refluxed in ethanol in presence of small amount of sodium iodide for 12 hr. The solid separated on cooling